

A Comparative Study on the Effectiveness of Mulligan Bent Leg Raising Vs Slump Stretching Along with SWD in Mechanical Low Back Pain

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ABSTRACT:

Problem statement: Low back pain [LBP] is the most frequent, self-reported type of musculoskeletal pain, is often recurrent and has important socio-economic consequences. Eighty percent of low back pains are due to “mechanical back pain” and are caused by back muscle strain or ligament sprain. The muscle strain and ligament sprain are due to sudden unaccustomed activities and improper posture.

Approach: The subjects were approached via Sri Venkateshwaraa Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Ariyur, Pondicherry-605 102.

Purpose: The purpose of the study was to find out the effectiveness of Mulligan Bent Leg Raising [MBLR] Vs Slump Stretching along with SWD to reduce pain and improve SLR in mechanical low back pain.

Results: The statistical analysis obtained from the unpaired t-test shows that the post-test values of Group A and Group B for a range of motion and pain are 5.39 ($p < 0.001$) and 5.43 ($p < 0.001$), respectively. The values obtained from the statistical analysis concluded that there is a significant difference between Group A and Group B, with Group A being more effective.

Conclusion: The study concluded that the Mulligan bent leg raising, along with SWD was effective in the treatment of mechanical low back pain among college students

KEYWORDS: Mulligan bent leg raising, Mechanical Low Back Pain, Short Wave Diathermy, Slump stretching.

INTRODUCTION

Low back pain is the most frequent, self-reported type of musculoskeletal pain, is often recurrent, and has important socio-economic consequences^[1]. Unilateral pain with no referral below the knee is called mechanical low back pain or lumbago. Mulligan bent leg raise is a painless technique indicated for patients with low back pain who has limited and or painful straight leg raising^[2]. Slump stretching is one of the techniques to improve motor function which involves the application of manual and mechanical force to elongate the structures that have adaptively shortened^[3].

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

This is a comparative study that includes 30 patients from the Department of Physiotherapy, Sri Venkateshwaraa Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Ariyur, Pondicherry-605 102. Subjects were divided into two groups (Group A- 15 & Group B- 15). The subjects were included based on the selection criteria. The inclusion criteria of the study were Subjects in the age group of 23 to 45 years, Having a unilateral limitation of SLR more than 45 degrees, Both genders included, Patients with low back pain mainly of the buttock or distal thigh pain, Subjects who are willing to participate in the study, and exclusion criteria were subjects with Presence of clinical features of low quarter neurological symptoms (e.g.): sensation loss, motor loss, abnormal reflexes, and bowel & bladder dysfunction, Patients with several spinal deformities, spondylosis, spondylolisthesis, lumbar canal stenosis, and disc herniation, Past history of major spinal surgery, Pregnancy, not willing to participate in the study. In both groups, the subject's pre-test and post-test values were collected using Goniometer for PSLR Range of Motion Measurements. Visual Analogue Scale for

Pain Ratings. The study was conducted for a period of 3 months and during the study time subjects received Group A Mulligan Bent Leg Raising and Group B Slump Stretching for a period of 4 weeks.

PROCEDURE

SWD:

Before giving MBLR and SLUMP stretching, SWD has been given to the patient with the coplanar method of electrode placement in the lumbar region for 15 15-minute duration in each session. Instruction has been given to the patient, to inform about more heat during the treatment period.

MULLIGAN BENT LEG RAISING

The patient’s position is supine lying at the edge of the couch. Hip and knee in 90-degree flexion and heel of the plinth. The therapist’s position is to walk stance on the affected side. Hand placement is the shoulder of the inner hand is placed under the popliteal fossa. The therapist grasps the lower end of the thigh with both hands. The therapist applied longitudinal traction along the long axis of the femur. The therapist takes the hip into flexion until the first resistance is felt. If the therapist feels resistance due to muscle tightness or if the patient feels stretch pain, the contract-relax technique is applied by asking the patient to push the therapist’s shoulder gently [hold for five seconds]. Now the therapist can take the patient’s hip into further flexion if pain-free. If patients feel pain during the maneuver, the hip can be moved into abduction or external rotation/more traction before further hip flexion is added. Hold that position for 20 seconds and repeat it for three times in one session. MBLR has been performed in four sessions per week for a period of 4 weeks.

SLUMP STRETCHING

The patient is seated on the edge of the couch with the legs supported, the hips in a neutral position, and hands clasping the hand by a side. First, the therapist should slump the back into thoracic & lumbar flexion. The therapist then uses one arm to apply overpressure across the shoulders to maintain flexion of the thoracic & lumbar spine. Then, the therapist applies overpressure to the cervical region and maintains the flexion of the whole spine [cervical, thoracic, lumbar]. On the other hand, the therapist holds the patient’s foot in maximum dorsiflexion for 30sec and 3 times in 1 session. Four sessions have been performed in a week for 4 weeks duration.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS:

The data obtained were analyzed using both the paired and unpaired t-test and were tabulated. The calculated ‘t’ value obtained from paired ‘t-test of group A (within group analysis) of the PSLR & VAS test for 14 degrees of freedom and 5% level of significance was 32.63 & 49.95 and group B were 13.45 & 33.8 with the p-value <0.05 (Table 1) In the statistical analysis obtained from the PSLR & VAS, the mean values and SD obtained from Group A and Group B PSLR were 21.93 ± 2.604, VAS was 46.66 ± 3.619, and PSLR 14.93 ± 4.300, VAS was 38.66 ± 4.419 respectively. For 28 degrees of freedom and a 5% level of significance, the calculated ‘t’ value of PSLR and VAS are 5.39 and 5.43 respectively (Table 2).

TABLE 1: PAIRED ‘T’ TEST VALUES:

GROUP		MEAN		SD		Calculated ‘t’ value		Table ‘t’ value	P VALUE	
		PSLR	VAS	PSLR	VAS	PSLR	VAS		PSLR	VAS
GROUP A	PRE-TEST	60.73	66.33	3.807	5.814	32.63	49.95	2.14	<0.05	<0.05
	POST -TEST	82.66	19.66	4.715	5.164					
GROUP B	PRE-TEST	58.66	65.66	5.703	5.627	13.45	33.88	2.14	<0.05	<0.05
	POST -TEST	73.6	27.66	2.772	4.952					

GRAPH 1: WITHIN-GROUP ANALYSIS OF BOTH GROUP A AND GROUP B:

TABLE 2: GROUPS A & B BETWEEN GROUP ANALYSIS

AKE					t – Value		p-value	
GROUPS	MEAN		SD		PSLR	VAS	PSLR	VAS
	PSLR	VAS	PSLR	VAS				
GROUP – A	56.88	57.54	7.671	7.390	41.336	40.436	<0.001	<0.001
GROUP – B	53.33	53.54	8.052	7.389				

GRAPH 2: BETWEEN-GROUP ANALYSIS OF GROUP A AND GROUP B:

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the present study was to compare the effectiveness of Mulligan Bent Leg Raising versus Slump Stretching along with SWD for reducing pain and improving SLR in patients with mechanical low back pain. The result of the study demonstrated

that group A Mulligan Bent Leg Raising and group B Slump Stretching show significance in PSLR & VAS. Group A little more effective than Group B. And it strongly supports the earlier findings of **Gajendrakumar Patel (2014)**, the purpose of this study was to **Compare the Effectiveness of Mulligan Bent Leg Raising and Slump Stretching in Patients with Low Back Pain**. The conclusion of this study shows MBLR techniques significantly reduce pain and improve ROM of PSLR than the slumping technique [2]. **Rimpy Jain, Unaise Ahmed Hameed (2012) Effectiveness of Slump Stretching in Comparison to Conventional Physiotherapy in Treatment of Subacute Non-radicular Low Back Pain**. The result shows that the analysis of The significant differences was found at the end of the 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th week ($p=0.0185$, $p=0.000$, $p=0.000$ and $p=0.000$, respectively) between the two groups, in favor of the experimental group. The analysis of MODI scores between both the groups suggested that there were significant differences at the end of 1st week ($p=0.4375$), 2nd week ($p=0.4515$), 3rd week ($p=0.078$), and 4th week ($p=0.0865$). However, at the follow-up (5th week), a significant difference was found between the two groups. The conclusion of this study is a combination of slump stretching and conventional physiotherapy is more effective than conventional physiotherapy alone in reducing pain in patients with non-radicular subacute LBP [7]. This study results also show strong evidence of the study conducted by **Saunabh Gupta (2006)** In his study, he assessed **The Immediate Effects of the Mulligan Bent Leg Raise Technique on Limited Straight Leg Raise in Mechanical Low Back Pain Patients**. However, 24h later, there was a significant increase in the range by 7 degrees in the BLR group, which may be clinically important. In addition, there was a one-point reduction in pain, but no difference between groups [8]. These results show similar effects to my study concluded that both group show effectiveness in that Group A Mulligan Bent Leg Raising is more effective than Group B Slump Stretching in Mechanical Low Back Pain [8].

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that Group A - Mulligan Bent Leg Raising is more effective than Group B - Slump Stretching in Mechanical Low Back Pain patients. Limitations are a Limited number of subjects, Vast difference in the age group which ranges from 23-45 years, Long term follow-up to 4 weeks in which patients found it difficult to cope with the schedule, Randomized study groups were taken, Subjects from all professional and thus different activity levels were included and may be a source of variation in results, Only used in two outcome measurement scale. Recommendations are In future studies the number of patients can be increased, Home programs like self-stretching can be included in further studies, Ergonomic changes can also be included if required in future trials.

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Cite this Article: S. Ramkumar, Bharaneedharan T., Dharshini Chittybabu, D. (2025). A Comparative Study on the Effectiveness of Mulligan Bent Leg Raising Vs Slump Stretching Along with SWD in Mechanical Low Back Pain. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(5), pp. 2179-2183. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i5-26>